
Combined Impact Of Kisan Credit Card And Pm (Kisan) Scheme On Production And Economic Capability Of Farmers In Gondia District

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Abstract:

Agriculture is a prominent industry and livelihood provider in many countries but it is the soul of India. Agriculture needs credit for the preparation of land, sowing of seed, and finally proper care of crop and it gets ready to sell at an affordable cost. The Kisan Credit Card is a pioneer in providing agriculture loans, Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana is another tool for providing financial support to farmers governed by the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmer Welfare. Both schemes are central sector schemes implemented where special preference is given to small and marginal farmers for providing financial assistance for attaining multiple needs. The loan amount KCC will be determined based on landholding and operational capacity of farmers, DLTC & SLTC recommended the credit limit based on the scale of production of the cardholder. The presented paper has gathered data from the Gondia district in Maharashtra. The majority of farmer respondents experienced that the scheme was moderately helpful in addressing the needs of farmers and realized that the scheme played a significant role in improving their standard of living, due to the high rate of inflation the scheme could not give any big change in their lifestyle and dependency on the Indigenous bank.

Keywords: Kisan Credit Card, PM Kisan credit, Direct Benefit Transfer, agriculture credit.

Introduction:

Agriculture is a common occupation among low and middle-income people who are subject to various risks that make it difficult for them to continue their livelihood until crops are harvested.

The majority of the village population depends on crop production and is contingent on allied activities. Agriculture is an essential segment of economic development as well and is also a key factor for India's GDP, this is the reason that the government has a soft corner for the sector. In the changing scenario of advancement, the best possible utilization of available resources at the maximum level requires an adequate supply of credit to the agriculture sector. The Kisan credit card scheme is

prominent in providing crop loans in an affordable and timely manner. The PM Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana is another scheme that plays a vital role in alleviating poverty in the community of poor farmers. The government runs a mix of policies to provide financial assistance with a reliable consumption floor for the most vulnerable rural resident, fertilizers subsidiary, and social transfer they found helpful for improving their condition, social transfer schemes were found to have beneficial but limited impact on equality. India currently, has 313 schemes under 53 ministers that use the mechanism of DBT. Pradhan Mantri Kisan Samman Nidhi is under Agriculture and Farmer's Welfare (MOAFW) a Central sectors scheme implemented by the

Government of India. A DBT annual of Rs6000/-in 3 equal installments of Rs2000/-each SMF in a gap of 4 monthly periods yearly.

Schemes Potential to the SMF in Gondia District:

- 1) **Level of Satisfaction:** To what extent does the respondent perceive gratification in the timeline, sufficiency, procedure, and graveled redressed mechanism?
- 2) **Utility of the fund:** To what extent the funds are purposeful in meeting the basic convenience of the farmers?
- 3) **Preserve:** The extent to which the respondents, able to manage adverse conditions, and risk pressure that are involved in farming.
- 4) **Useful Contribution:** To what extent did farmers perceive the various inputs for farming as beneficial to the respondent?

Table A: Economy And Agriculture District Gondia state Maharashtra

No. of cultivators hold land less than 2 Hect	306553
No. of cultivators hold land above 2 Hect-5 Hect	53754
No. of total cultivators	360,307

Method of Data Analysis and Collection:

The selection criteria are based on reference for whether or not the scheme is helping the welfare of the common section of SMF, the dimension of the study was discovered by review of relevant literature and expert opinion. Gondia is famous for the production of different crops like Tur, Jawas, Til, and many others. The district is divided into talukas name (i) Gondia (ii) Amgaon (iii) Deori (iv) Salekasa (v) Tirora (vi) Sadak Arjuni (vii) Morgaon Arjuni (viii) Goregaon. The sampling frame of the beneficiaries of PM-KISAN was prepared

and 40 respondents from each taluka were selected using stratified disproportional simple random sampling of small and marginal farmers for the study. Thus 320 respondents were surveyed through live questioners list is prepared for the accuracy of the result. The Productivity of the PM-KSNY is prepared based on three are as follows:

The **PMKSNY** scheme helps farmers adopt modern agricultural techniques to obtain better yields and also leads to protecting farmers' liquidity constraints and ceasing access

Schemes Potential to the SMF in Gondia District:

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Result and Discussion:

Results of the study are presented as follows, Fund Utilization, Level of Satisfaction, and Coping Capabilities.

Table 1 revealed that 67.5 percent of the respondents agreed with the statement that fund is utilized in the education of children followed by 47.5 percent undecided with it and 5 percent disagreed with it. Regarding Expenditure in Food Consumption showed that 64.17 percent of the respondents agreed with it 25 percent of

respondents were undecided about it whereas 10.83 percent disagreed. About Expenditure in Health and Medical, 64.17 percent of the respondents agreed.

In the case of Household Expenditure, 41.67 percent disagreed as well as 37.5 percent of the respondents were undecided about it whereas 21.25 percent agreed with it

Table 1: Distribution of beneficiaries based on Utility of the fund (n=320)

Statement	A f(%)	UD f(%)	DA f(%)
Investment in Education	184(67.5)	120(47.5)	16 (5)
Expenditure in Food Consumption	205 (64.17)	80 (25)	34 (10.83)
Expenditure in Health and Medical	205 (64.17)	86(27)	10(26.65)
Household Expenditure	68(21.25)	120(37.5)	132(41.25)

Table 2 : Distribution of beneficiaries Level of Satisfaction

Statement	A f(%)	UD f(%)	DA f(%)
Financial support is adequate	32(10)	192(60)	96(30)
Financial support is timely	128(40)	128(40)	64(20)
The procedure for obtaining credit support was convenient	104(32.5)	143(44.09)	80(25)
The grievance redressal mechanism is lucid	176(55.15)	130(40.625)	14(4.375)

Table 2 shows revealed 60 percent of the beneficiaries are undecided about an adequacy amount 30 percent of the beneficiaries disagree with it, and 40 percent beneficiary are equally satisfied in financial support is in timely and 40 say they are

undecided about it, where 44.69 percent undecided that procedure for obtaining the credit support convenient, 32.5 are agreed with it, where 55.15 percent are agreed and 40.625 percent are undecided with grievance redressed mechanism is lucid.

Table 3: Distribution of beneficiaries based on Coping Capability (n=320)

Statement	A f(%)	UD f(%)	Df(%)
The ability to withstand the risk of adoption of new technology has increased	44(13.75)	176(55)	100(31.25)
Capability to withstand the risk of diseased incidence and pest control	48(15)	120(37.5)	152(47.5)
The ability to bear the fluctuation in market price has increased	76(17.187)	120(37.5)	124(45.313)
The ability to endure the vagaries of the weather has increased	48(15)	192(60)	80(25)

Table 3 reveals that 55 percent of the beneficiaries are undecided and 31.25 percent disagree with the ability to withstand the risk from the adoption of new technology has increased, where 37.5 percent of responses recorded are undecided about the capability to withstand the risk from diseased incidence and pest control.

Regarding the ability to bear the fluctuation in market price, 45.313 percent disagreed 37.5 percent were undecided and 17.187 percent disagreed with it on the other hand 60 percent of respondents were undecided 25 percent disagreed and 15 percent agreed that the scheme can endure the vagaries of the weather has increased.

Table 4: Analysis of the response recorded under different categories

Categories(%between)	Frequency			Total
Low(10-40)	6	7	8	21
Moderate(40-70)	5	4	4	13
High>70	-	-	-	

Conclusion:

The overall effectiveness index of the model was worked out by taking into all four dimensions of productivity, viz(i) Utility of Fund (ii) Level of Satisfaction (iii) Coping Capability. The respondents were classified from low to high productivity index scores based on the cumulative cube root frequency method. Table 5 revealed that in Gondia District most responses recorded lied on low, i.e., 21 level of satisfaction with the PM-KISAN scheme, and 13 respondents are lied in Moderately productive which presents that the scheme is less productive in eradicating their poverty and coping with their day-to-day needs, it is visible that in Table: **Utility of the fund**, revealed 67.5 percent respondent agreed that financial support is utilized for education of their children and 47.5 percent are undecided with it, where on the same table 64.17 percent beneficiaries using the fund for food consumption on the other hand 41.25 percent of the beneficiaries are disagree that, the fund was utilized for household expenditure. Table 2 **Level of Satisfaction** revealed that 40, 40 percent agreed and were undecided that the financial support is received in a timely and 55.15 percent that the Grievance redressed mechanism is lucid, and 40 percent were undecided about it, where 44.09 percent were undecided that the scheme's procedure for obtaining credit support was convenient. Table 3 **Coping Capability** revealed that 55 percent of the beneficiaries are undecided and 31.25 disagree that the scheme's ability to withstand the risk of new technology has increased. Whereas, 47.5 percent and 37.5 percent were undecided about the scheme's

capability to withstand the risk of disease incidence and pest control. In the same table, 60 percent of the beneficiaries are undecided that the scheme's ability to endure the vagaries of the weather has increased. These are the real behaviors recorded by the beneficiaries of Gondia in Maharashtra where beneficiaries are given different views about their experiences of the scheme. The purpose of the study was to know whether the scheme helps eradicate poverty but due high inflation rate community of farmers is not getting sufficient results the Maharashtra Government has planned to increase the financial support so we can expect in coming days the problems may resolved to some extent.

Eligible Condition for the benefits of the scheme:

- The farmer must be a citizen of Maharashtra.
- Land that may be farmed should be farmed should be registered in his name.
- Cultivator must have a bank account to be enrolled under the PMKSNY.
- The KYC procedure has been mandatory to guarantee that the advantage has reached the intended cultivator.

This scheme is expected to benefit 11.59 million farmers in the state. The state Govt was rolling out the scheme when it found that 1.33 million beneficiaries who are technically not eligible but have somehow made it to the list of eligible beneficiaries under the PMKSN have also received a sum of Rs1554 crore in 4 years as beneficiaries

according to the data from the state SAD the desired results.
the recovery process started but did not get

Table: A: Following data presented by the Department of Agriculture, Cooperation and Farmers Welfare.

Ministry of Agriculture and Welfare of Farmers - Gondia District

A	B	C	D	E
Total Beneficiary	Beneficiary who received First Installment	Beneficiary of who received Second Installment	Beneficiary who received the Third Installment	A beneficiary who received the Fourth Installment
268364	267319	265893	248807	218651
No of Bene Reduce in every succeeding installment	1045(A-B)	1426(B-C)	17086(C-D)	30156(D-E)

The table clearly shows that this reduced number of beneficiary trends trying to take our focus toward the following points

As per some previous years' studies, we have observed that there was a trend of reduction in the numbers of beneficiaries due to technical reasons as they were not aware of the KYC update procedure but many people realized relief after getting income support from the scheme even children's of poor farmers who drop out after middle-class school education they register for higher classes.

The story of Indian education is one of quantitative progress but conspicuous failure in quality. After six decades, India has made notable improvements in gross and net enrolment ratios and achieved universal enrolment in lower primary education.

Opinion of Beneficiaries Farmers about PM-Kisan Scheme:

1. More than ninety percent of beneficiaries of the scheme opine that the amount is inadequate to cover even the basic level needs of the farmers.
2. The scheme is specially provided to benefit small and marginal farmers but ignores landless and tenant farmers,

though they also play a vital role in dividing responsibilities, costs, and risks.

3. To devise innovative procedures to eliminate absentee landlordism should be identified and cautioned as they do not function as primary cultivators or tillers of land.
4. The registration process should be simplified as most beneficiaries belong to remote areas and face various difficulties in the KYC process.
5. DAT of money to farmers' bank accounts, pilferage would also be less. This encourages farmers to open bank accounts in Jan -Dhan Yojana and link Aadhar with bank accounts.
6. Land record needs to be Digitalized and updated regularly basis may result in resolving the difficulties of farmers who partitioned their holdings from other family members may lead to them being a disclaimer of the scheme if land records are not updated and simultaneously identifying the fraudulent claims should avoided.
7. Awareness programs should be organized at the village level by KVK to propagate the benefit of the

schemes, so the eligible excluded farmers of the village will get an opportunity to enroll themselves under this scheme.

Future Scope:

The scheme initially targeted small and marginal farmers but did not cover tenancy farmers. The number of beneficiaries is reducing, possibly due to the KYC procedure, bank accounts, or Aadhar cards being difficult tasks for the illiterate. Verification of land ownership documents under the scheme is mandatory, but challenging in remote areas.

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List of Acronym

PMKSNS		PM Kisan Samman Nidhi scheme
DMT	-	Direct Money Transfer
KSNY	-	Kisan Samman Nidhi Yojana
MOAFW	-	Ministry Of Agriculture Farmer's Welfare
SMF	-	Small and Marginal Farmers
SG	-	State Government
SAD	-	State Agriculture Department
